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The higher education environment driving academic library strategy: A political, economic, social and technological (PEST) analysis

John Cox*

National University of Ireland Galway, Ireland

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ABSTRACT

The higher education environment is a key operating context for academic libraries and many political, economic, social and technological (PEST) factors shape it. This article examines these factors, their influence on higher education during the past two decades and their implications for libraries. Library literature tends to cover the higher education environment peripherally despite its influence. Using the established PEST analysis methodology, the article foregrounds higher education throughout and finds major ongoing changes across all four dimensions globally, creating challenges and opportunities for libraries. The conclusion notes briefly some possible future implications of the global coronavirus crisis and highlights the importance for library operations and strategy of monitoring and understanding developments in higher education.

Introduction

The higher education climate in which libraries operate has changed significantly since 2000, driven by a series of political, economic, social and technological forces. Government policy in many countries has been to reduce the role of the state in funding higher education, leaving universities and other institutions to compete in an open market for alternative sources of revenue. Economic circumstances are difficult at institutions which are less successfully competitive, and the impact of the global recession starting in 2008 continues to exert negative influence. Tuition fees are often a vital element in institutional funding. Students may need to take out loans to pay these fees, creating financial pressures for many while fueling a more consumerist approach towards education and employability. The student body itself has become more diverse in social and demographic terms. This in turn generates demand for more flexible pathways to academic qualifications, possibly over several years and with an increasing dependence on online learning technologies. Most recently, the 2020 coronavirus outbreak has convulsed higher education.

The preceding paragraph highlights just a sample of the manifestations of change in higher education. There is a recognition that academic libraries should align their strategies and services closely with the priorities of their parent institutions (Oakleaf, 2010). To do so it is important to understand the higher education environment influencing the direction being taken by the institution. That environment is complex, evolving and affected by many factors, often beyond the control of

any institution or its library but potentially vital in determining the future of both.

The objective of this article is to identify and examine the key political, economic, social and technological factors shaping higher education internationally and to consider their implications for academic libraries. The article aims to inform academic library strategy, planning and positioning, while recognizing that the importance of any factor or combination of factors will vary by country and institution. This contribution to the literature is unique in that it foregrounds the higher education environment for libraries throughout rather than referencing it peripherally as a backdrop to library themes. It also applies the PEST (Political, Economic, Social and Technological) analysis methodology (PESTLEanalysis, 2014) to the wider higher education environment. This methodology has not featured strongly in previous library literature. The current article attempts to provide insights into how the higher education climate plays out in life on campus from the perspectives of academics, students, leaders and other stakeholders, as well as those of library staff.

A review of the literature on the higher education climate and its influence, including some material beyond that published by library authors, is followed by a description of the PEST analysis methodology, outlining its scope, value and limitations. Separate sections for each of the political, economic, social and technological dimensions examine issues under these headings which influence higher education. Each of these sections incorporates a discussion of the implications for academic libraries of the factors identified. The article concludes with

* James Hardiman Library, National University of Ireland Galway, Galway H91 REW4, Ireland.

E-mail address: john.cox@nuigalway.ie.

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some comments on the challenges and opportunities this nexus of influences creates for library strategy, noting also some possible future implications for higher education of the global coronavirus crisis.

Literature review

Higher education literature

Publications outside the library literature represent a valuable source for anyone seeking a general appreciation of the higher education environment, internationally or for different geographic regions. The *2020 EDUCAUSE Horizon Report, Teaching and Learning Edition* provides global coverage (Brown et al., 2020). Technology developments in teaching and learning provide the context for a brief overview of political, economic, social and technological influences. It also examines four possible 2030 scenarios: growth, constraint, collapse and transformation.

For the United States, Geiger (2019) offers a history of developments since the Second World War, incorporating the influence of government policy and a full analysis of the current situation. He emphasizes major expansion and increases in participation, but expresses reservations too, for example, regarding inequality of access, provider stratification and selectivity, rising costs, student debt, and the quality of education and learning. Fitzpatrick (2019) provides the perspective of a leading US humanities scholar. She calls for generous thinking, collaboration and a focus on contributing to the public good as a counterbalance to what she sees as an overly competitive environment arising especially from a reduction in government support for higher education. The Ithaka Next Wave conference, held annually since 2016, captures thinking about directions in higher education in the United States; its focus in 2019 was the influence of technological and social trends on research and learning (Ithaka, 2020).

Similar to Fitzpatrick in outlook and purpose, but less restrained in tone is a book called *The Good University* by Raewyn Connell, a retired Australian social sciences researcher (Connell, 2019). Her commentary reflects Australian experience but is international in scope, representing a critique of neoliberalist government policy and marketization in higher education. She outlines a series of concerns from an academic perspective, highlighting anger on campus, the weight of accountability and a lack of autonomy before making counterproposals for universities focused on creativity and challenge, cooperation, equity of access and tangible social engagement.

Turning to Britain, a Universities UK publication on *Patterns and Trends in UK Higher Education 2017* includes coverage of emerging demographic, technological, economic and political trends (Universities UK, 2017). Although the focus is on the UK, this document helpfully outlines in generally applicable terms the impact on higher education institutions of factors such as government policy, demographics, international recruitment markets, technology, and the state of the global economy. Shattock and Horvath (2019) describe the evolution of British government policy and are critical of some of its consequences for institutions, notably in terms of governance.

Developments in Europe are the subject of the Third Future of Education – Bologna Process Researchers Conference. Its proceedings encompass 42 papers, reflecting experience across Europe on themes such as internationalization, university rankings, widening participation, accountability and governance (Curaj et al., 2018). Market forces and European Union interventions to integrate higher education standards and qualifications across its constituent countries feature in another edited volume on European policy (Sin et al., 2019).

Library literature

As already noted, the library literature tends to treat the higher education environment as a background topic. It features more prominently in some publications, however. One of these is the collection

of essays to mark the 75th anniversary of the Association of College and Research Libraries in 2015 (Bell et al., 2015). The higher education climate is the context for numerous contributions. Dempsey's introduction emphasizes developments in education, technology and scholarly publishing and their influence on teaching and research. In consecutive chapters Bell reflects on students' desire for flexible routes to academic qualifications as well as shifting demographics in the student body. Towards the end Fister notes a focus by higher education institutions on metrics to justify the cost of academic programs and raises questions for libraries on whether they place enough emphasis on democracy, public good and social responsibility in such an environment. Also focused on the US is a book by Budd (2018) on changes in academic libraries which includes a chapter on the state of higher education in that country, defining the different categories of colleges and universities in addition to providing an overview of commentator critiques of the system as a whole.

A UK report on mapping the future of academic libraries identifies "intensified contextual pressures – a myriad of political, economic and other pressures" (Pinfield et al., 2017, p. 4) in relation to higher education and libraries, including funding challenges, increased competition and government evaluation of teaching and research. A graphic lists 30 key trends across political, economic, social and technological dimensions emerging from a survey of library staff. This high number is seen as reflective of a lack of consensus which translates into a concerning degree of uncertainty about the future in another paper based on the same research (Cox, Pinfield, & Rutter, 2019a). An earlier overview of the changing higher education context also noted that "Working with uncertainty is our new 'normal state'" (Davies, 2013, p. 2), indicating the challenges library staff face in a changing climate which the author highlights as increasingly global and competitive. Earlier still is an article by Atkinson (2003) which includes a PEST analysis of external factors influencing change management and the embedding of innovation in libraries. Some of these factors endure today, notably marketization, globalization and funding pressures, while others have emerged more strongly in the interim, for example consumerist views of higher education, a focus on employability and an increased diversity in the student body.

The higher education environment is a key context for a literature review on positioning the academic library in the institution which includes sections on senior stakeholder perceptions, student success, and institutional reputation and impact (Cox, 2018). Gwyer's (2018) overview of future trends impacting academic libraries includes the changing higher education climate as a significant trend, noting a more consumerist environment in which there is a particularly strong focus on the student experience. She identifies areas for skills development by libraries in this climate, including proof of value, impact and return on investment. Oakleaf (2010) summarizes high expectations of higher education by stakeholders, including government, and strongly emphasizes the issue of accountability, with implications for how libraries demonstrate value to their institutions. Alignment of library services and resources to institutional missions is seen as vital and this theme recurs in the literature. In adapting McKinsey's 7S model to conceptualize the issues of alignment for academic libraries, Cox, Pinfield, & Rutter, 2019b include alignment with the wider situation or context. They see political and economic aspects as important, but particularly challenging due to their complexity and unpredictability which place them beyond the control of libraries and indeed their parent institutions.

Alignment with institutional directions is the focus of the *University Futures, Library Futures* research project by Ithaka and OCLC (Malpas et al., 2018). This research identifies a trend towards diversification of mission by higher education institutions to achieve distinctiveness in a crowded provider marketplace and categorizes institutions into three types: research, liberal education and career preparation, each serving different audiences. The expectation is that libraries will adapt their services according to institutional focus, and the research finds some

evidence that this is happening, although differences in provision are not yet as pronounced as might be anticipated. The authors urge libraries to pay more attention to how best to support the needs of what they term the “new-traditional student profile” (p. 21) which is more diverse in background, age and career stage.

It may be reasonable to view the extent and perceived success of alignment with the institutional mission as a barometer of the library's understanding of the higher education environment. There is, however, evidence of alignment efforts falling short, at minimum in terms of levels of recognition by stakeholders or of effective communication to them. More than 200 provosts responded to a 2016 survey by [Murray and Ireland \(2018\)](#) about their perceptions of academic library value. The most common view among the provosts was that academic libraries were only “somewhat involved” in areas of priority for the institution such as student success and faculty research productivity; furthermore, the provosts did not recognize the potential for the library to support student retention. [Saunders' \(2016\)](#) examination of 63 academic library strategies provides further insights. She found a greater focus on library functions than on institutional priorities, with only 27% of these library strategies making explicit connections with the institutional plan and 11% including goals specific to student success factors.

A study of the perceptions of executive leadership at UK universities included exhortations to library directors to become more involved in addressing challenging issues facing their institutions, not only those confronting the library ([Baker & Alden, 2017](#)). This suggestion of a library-centric mindset also surfaces in research by [Salisbury & Peseta \(2018\)](#) which finds the library voice largely absent from campus debates about the idea of the university during what they see as a “crisis of purpose” (p. 245) for universities. They attribute that silence to a library tendency favoring a practice-based perspective over conceptual thinking about the changing environment. [Dempsey and Malpas \(2018\)](#) observe that discussion about the future of academic libraries “often proceeds without reference to the universities of which libraries are a part” (p. 67). Any such approach carries risks for academic libraries which they can mitigate through a stronger understanding of the higher education environment and the forces shaping it.

Methodology

This article uses the PEST analysis technique to examine the higher education environment. PEST analysis is a long-established methodology, commonly applied in business “for understanding the external macro-environment in which an organization operates” ([Ross, 2008](#), p. 49). The PEST acronym stands for Political, Economic, Social and Technological, representing the types of factors identified in the analysis. The technique accommodates some flexibility, for example replacing Social with Sociocultural or extending PEST to PESTLE to include legal and environmental factors.

PEST analysis focuses on external influences and the impact they may have on an organization, country or sector. Potential benefits of applying this methodology include guiding strategic decision-making and gaining competitive advantage, as well as achieving positive alignment with external forces and avoiding errors that could compromise effective performance ([Heery & Noon, 2017](#); [Ross, 2008](#)). It helpfully complements a related technique, SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) analysis, to provide a full picture from both the inside and the outside. Conversely, one of the limitations of PEST analysis is that it is considered insufficient on its own for strategy development, requiring in addition the use of other tools such as SWOT and competitive industry analysis. PEST analysis may be time-consuming, so broad in range that only some factors may be relevant or may focus on issues that impact very differently in individual regions ([Analoui & Karami, 2003](#); [Halaychik, 2016](#); [Smith & Raspin, 2008](#)).

It is important to understand the nature and scope of each of the four dimensions: political, economic, social and technological ([PESTLEanalysis, 2014](#)). In the business environment, a key political

issue is the extent of government intervention in the economy, while the economic dimension accommodates data such as inflation, interest and exchange rates. Social factors include lifestyles, education, immigration and emigration, while technology encompasses the potential for efficiencies and new value for customers. Many of these factors are relevant for higher education too, but it is necessary to adapt PEST analysis to this context and [Martinez and Wolverson \(2009\)](#) provide valuable guidance. They identify government regulation as an important political factor, influencing issues such as governance, accountability and funding, and recognize the vulnerability of higher education to economic recessions. Demographics, especially in the 18–24 age category, and attitudes to the value or relevance of a college education, emerge as important social factors, as does the influence of technology on learning and research. The *2020 EDUCAUSE Horizon Report* is another source for PEST factors specific to higher education ([Brown et al., 2020](#)).

The application of PEST analysis has found limited coverage in the library literature to date. [Moran and Morner \(2018\)](#) and [Halaychik \(2016\)](#) introduce this technique as one of a number of tools available to libraries for planning purposes, while [Atkinson \(2003\)](#) includes PEST analysis to generate a list of drivers for change for libraries in the context of managing change and embedding innovation. Other library applications relate to factors influencing resource sharing ([Goldner & Birch, 2012](#)) and collaboration ([Buchanan et al., 2012](#)). More recently, [Kaspar \(2018\)](#) outlines the merits of PEST analysis as a versatile framework for environmental scanning by libraries seeking to understand the forces at work in higher education. She adapts the model for academic libraries to highlight factors influencing their key user constituencies and creating strategic engagement opportunities.

The emphasis that PEST analysis places on external factors across four dimensions with a strong influence on higher education provides confidence in applying it to this environment as a key operating context for academic libraries. The next sections examine political, economic, social and technological drivers and their impact on higher education institutions, including some particular implications for their libraries. The approach is selective for reasons of space, highlighting those factors which seem to exert the strongest impact on institutions and are most likely to influence library strategy. Although there is a separate section for each of the four dimensions it is important to note that they are interdependent, resulting in some overlap of coverage across the sections. The global coronavirus crisis emerged during the writing of this article. It is referenced occasionally, and primarily in the conclusion, recognizing that its longer-term implications for higher education will be profound but will become clearer in the future.

Political factors influencing higher education

Government intervention surfaced as a key point in the earlier description of the political dimension of the PEST methodology. This is a significant issue for higher education where a declining role for the state in relation to funding has been evident for some time. In many countries, notably the United States, Australia and England, governments have opted for an approach, variously described as marketization, privatization or neoliberalism, whereby institutions operate and compete in a self-regulating free market with minimal state intervention. The intent is that competition should drive up quality, improve efficiency, deliver better value for money and offer more choice for consumers than when state funding predominates. Higher education has experienced a major reduction in government funding and one estimate is that the share of public expenditure on tertiary education in the UK fell from 80% in 1995 to 30% in 2009 ([Lybeck, 2018](#), p. 55), while a decline from 90% in the 1970s to 42% in 2010 is cited for Australia ([Connell, 2019](#), p. 118). Tuition fees, rising significantly over time and increasingly paid via student loans, have primarily filled the funding gap.

Other higher education policy issues preoccupy governments. One

of these is to increase and widen participation, especially among people from disadvantaged backgrounds who traditionally have not gone to university. This objective has met with some success. Geiger (2019, p. 314) notes an increase in enrollments from 15 million to 20 million in the United States between 2000 and 2016, while the UK had record numbers of students from disadvantaged backgrounds in higher education in 2015/16 (Universities UK, 2017, p. 63). Globally, the percentage of the relevant age group participating in higher education more than trebled from 10% in 1970 to 36% in 2015, with figures of over 50% for some countries (Connell, 2019, p. 3).

There is something of a paradox between the non-interventionist approach evident in governments' reduced role in funding and their increased emphasis on accountability for higher education. Governments can regulate the governance structures of higher education institutions, including the extent of lay representation, with implications for local autonomy. State concern with assessing the quality and impact of teaching and research has grown, resulting, for example, in the Research Excellence Framework (REF) in the UK and more recently the Teaching Excellence Framework (TEF) in England. The ability of an institution in England to raise its tuition fee cap in line with annual inflation will be linked in future to scores awarded in the TEF (Universities UK, 2017).

Student employability is a matter of interest to the state in many instances, influencing the curriculum or facilitating competition by alternative, often private, providers beyond the university sector whose focus may be more vocational (Fielden & Middlehurst, 2017). Foreign policy can significantly impact the internationalization strategies of higher education institutions through the closeness or otherwise of relations with other countries. Brexit, the withdrawal of the UK from the European Union, is a prominent example, with anticipated consequences for funding, recruitment and research collaboration (Universities UK, 2017). Other areas of state regulation with potential to affect higher education operations include research commercialization, immigration, safety, accessibility for people with disability, and copyright.

How do higher education institutions experience this range of political influences? The combination of reduced state funding and increased accountability to government, although by now often an established feature of the institutional operating environment, continues to generate many concerns. Whether all of these concerns are attributable to government policy is debatable, but they contribute towards the political sentiment on many campuses. This is so, despite expansion in higher education and increasing student numbers. Connell captures this paradox when she notes that "Prosperity and the problems of universities are closely linked" (Connell, 2019, p. 8).

Intense competition between institutions, discussed in the section on economic factors, can translate into a lack of collegiality on campus as departments or individuals pursue their own interests primarily. Fitzpatrick (2019) describes this tendency as competitive individualism, linking it especially to the academic reward system which favors publication in high-impact journals and takes limited account of service to the institution. The same author sees other negative consequences in the loss of government funding, notably a displacement of state responsibility onto private citizens who are often burdened by loan debt as their means of paying tuition fees, and a focus by institutions on financial sustainability instead of public good. She sees a tension between the traditional role of the university as producer and disseminator of knowledge and a newer paradigm as producer and disseminator of market-oriented credentials.

Government emphasis on accountability is another focus of criticism. This can result in a huge amount of administrative effort to generate reports, metrics and evidence of compliance with requirements. Connell (2019, p. 129) quotes an estimate that 8% of the national teaching budget in the UK is spent on quality assurance measures and posits that auditing reflects distrust between staff and managers, observing that decision-making is now concentrated in smaller

management groups. Shattock & Horvath (2019) are clear in their view that the evolution of university governance structures in the UK since 1992 has promoted top-down decision-making at the expense of participation in strategic policymaking by academic staff.

The lives of academic staff have changed too. Research at the University of York provides insights into the range of activities competing for their attention, including research, teaching, administration and publication, with particular pressure surrounding the last of these (Blake & Gallimore, 2018). Many lack job security as a result of what Macfarlane (2011, p. 66) calls "the increasing casualisation of the academic profession". In the United States Geiger (2019, p. 360) notes that "at the top 108 research universities, one-third of full-time faculty were not on tenure-track appointments in 2014". The tendency has been to deploy temporary staff to teaching roles, sometimes to enable academics to focus on research. There is a view that this reflects a devaluation of teaching and its relegation to "a Cinderella activity" (Macfarlane, 2011, p. 71). Unbundling of academic work, such that staff may perform either teaching or research but not both or may see support for areas such as academic writing migrate elsewhere can create a feeling of diminished status and of a hollowing-out of what it means to be an academic (Macfarlane, 2011).

Implications for libraries

Navigating this complex political climate on campus is not straightforward for libraries. Developing a position on marketization, where it is in operation, can be difficult as neoliberalist principles are likely to clash with library tenets of equality of access to knowledge and of learning as a public good. Nicholson (2015) is critical of libraries aligning with the neoliberalist philosophy through a "preoccupation with accountability and return on investment" (p. 330) which "changes what libraries are about" (p. 331), representing what the title of her article terms a "McDonaldization of academic libraries". She urges that libraries acknowledge neoliberalism but continue to advocate for education and libraries as public goods, helping to make higher education a transformative experience.

This dilemma is evident in research on the future of academic libraries in which library participants accepted metrics and demonstrating value for money as part of the operating environment but took a critical view, wishing to stay true to their professional values; as a result, libraries often reached an accommodation between competing pressures (Pinfield et al., 2017). These tensions may, however, represent an opportunity for libraries to participate in the campus debate and to emphasize their traditional values of neutrality, generosity and free speech as a counterbalance to other tendencies. The concerns felt by academics place a premium on critical thinking, collaboration, public engagement and openness, all of which libraries are well positioned to promote. The open scholarship movement, for instance, provides an opportunity for libraries to contribute towards addressing issues raised around systems for research assessment and academic reward.

The demands of accountability seem unavoidable, despite Nicholson's (2015) objections, and Oakleaf's (2010) recommendation that libraries link the value they offer to outcomes relative to the institution's priorities is well-targeted. This can help the library succeed in a difficult "internal market for resource, visibility and attention" (Appleton, 2018, p. 209) where competition for resources is often intense. Linkage to institutional priorities is important in securing influence with decision-makers, acknowledging the tighter-knit governance structures described earlier and their potential consequences for libraries in terms of increased distance from institutional leadership and strategic attention (Gwyer, 2018). Collegiality, support and attention for library initiatives from an increasingly busy and untenured academic staff cannot be taken for granted, but a close appreciation of academic pressures, perspectives, needs and concerns can serve libraries well. A similar level of understanding in relation to students can

Table 1
Summary of political factors and their influence

Political factor	Impact on higher education	Implications for libraries
Reduced role of state	Marketization, consumerism	Competition for resources
Widening participation policy	Increased student population	Supporting higher numbers
Accountability requirements	Tight governance, monitoring	Proof of value, impact
Performance expectations	Staff pressures, individualism	Changing relationships
Focus on research	Teaching/research tension	Balancing of support
Resistance to neoliberalism	Public good focus	Promotion of library values

be difficult to establish, given significant increases in the numbers and diversity of those participating in higher education, but student expectations feature prominently in the remaining sections of this PEST analysis. Table 1 summarizes political factors and their influence on higher education and academic libraries.

Economic factors influencing higher education

The influence of political factors is also evident in the economic environment for higher education, notably in the impact of marketization on funding, competition and student expectations. Higher education institutions, as mentioned previously, are vulnerable to government cuts and market forces at times of economic downturn. The global recession of 2008 hit hard at the time and has cast a long shadow since. Even in 2016 fewer than half of provosts at US universities or colleges agreed that it was over (Jaschik, 2016). To this can be added widespread expectation of a deep recession arising from the global coronavirus pandemic of 2020. Institutions in countries where state funding rather than marketization was the dominant model experienced a substantial reduction in government support from 2008. This was reported for the period between 2008 and 2016 at a third for Ireland, 21% for Spain and 11% for France; the same article cited an average decline of 11% per US state in the same period according to data from the State Higher Education Executive Officers Association (S. Baker, 2020).

Institutions face a challenging economic climate. Many have responded with a focus on maximizing operating efficiencies through measures such as reviewing course offerings, merging campuses or centralizing services. Administrators have, however, encountered limits to the extent and effectiveness of such efforts (Marcum, 2014). As a result, there is, except for countries such as Norway where higher education is free at public institutions, a strong reliance on revenue from tuition fees as state support has declined. Fees have been on the increase, rising, for example, from \$12,000 to \$26,000 or from \$33,000 to \$63,000 at comparable US public and private universities respectively between 2000 and 2015, inclusive of room and board (Geiger, 2019, p. 314). Government policy in England enabled universities to charge annual tuition fees of £9000 annually from 2012. Fees at such levels are often only affordable through student loans. Reliance on this source has generated escalating student debt, estimated in total at \$1250 billion in 2016 (Geiger, 2019, p. 315), while there has been a doubling to over 40% between 2002 and 2017 of the number of borrowers owing \$20,000 or more in student loans (Reiter & Ford, 2019, p. 618).

Competition between institutions has intensified for funding, donors, faculty, students, rankings and attention. Institutions may opt to differentiate from each other in order to improve their competitiveness, specializing in niche areas such as research, liberal education and career preparation, identified in a report by Ithaka and OCLC (Malpas et al., 2018). Geiger (2019) describes a dividing line between selective and open across three categories of private, public research and regional or community institutions in the United States. He also outlines competition from outside the university sector in the form of private, often for-profit, operators, termed alternative providers in England where the Higher Education and Research Act of 2017 has actively encouraged their presence in the market for students. Such institutions

are more vocational in mission than universities, potentially cheaper for students due to lower operating costs and strongly oriented towards flexible learning models, but have raised concerns regarding quality of education and economic viability (Fielden & Middlehurst, 2017).

Institutions compete on an international as well as a national basis, seeking to enhance their reputation and prestige by obtaining the highest possible position in the league tables of a range of global ranking systems. There is much criticism of these systems, often centered on a view that they fail to account for differences between type, distinctiveness or local context of institutions. Other concerns relate to perceived subjectivism, omissions in coverage and bias towards selectivity and wealth (Connell, 2019; Davies, 2013; Geiger, 2019). Nevertheless, institutions vie for ranking position, recognizing that this may influence student choice, staff recruitment or research funding awards. Attracting students from abroad is important not only in terms of diversity and internationalizing the curriculum, but also economically as these students often pay somewhat higher fees than their domestic counterparts. One source estimates non-European Union student fees at 23% of UK teaching income, with international sources supplying 16% of UK research income (Universities UK, 2017, p. 2).

Payment of high tuition fees, often via loans, has changed the relationship between students and their higher education institutions. The sums involved, and the prospect of substantial debt to be paid off after graduation, have promoted a consumerist view among students in which choice of where to study is fully informed by and decided on a range of published criteria, and expectations are higher and more difficult to satisfy. Students may take a more utilitarian view of higher education, assessing its costs and benefits primarily in economic terms (Pearson, 2018). Value for money has become a key performance indicator and the annual *Student Academic Experience Survey* in the UK measures student satisfaction in these terms (Higher Education Policy Institute, n.d.). Other surveys of student satisfaction have become well established and influential, including the US *National Survey of Student Engagement* (Indiana University, n.d., School of Education, Center for Postsecondary Research) which has equivalents in many countries.

Employability is a particular focus for students and may be seen as a return on investment in higher education. This has raised academic concerns that education has become “the making of human capital” (Connell, 2019, p. 118) and that government and employers are exerting excessive influence on the curriculum, with negative impact on the humanities (Fitzpatrick, 2019) and a shift from knowledge that academics want to produce to knowledge that business and governments want to consume (Pearson, 2018). The reality for institutions is that the focus on employability influences the development of academic programs in terms of their coverage, inclusion of work experience opportunities and the cultivation of partnerships with employers. The drive to meet rising student expectations can push up institutional expenditure too. In one example, spending on university buildings in England was estimated at £40 billion, financed by heavy borrowing, between 2002 and 2017 (Grove, 2018).

Implications for libraries

Academic libraries have long understood the importance of the economic climate as a key influence on their strategy and operations.

Economic realities are more concrete than political factors. Lewis (2016) recognizes one such reality when he points out that libraries can expect no long-term infusion of new money at a time when many institutions have stretched their efficiency measures to the limit. Value for money and cost control are key considerations in relation especially to the two largest categories of library expenditure, staffing and information resources. Many academic libraries have experienced cuts to their staffing budgets, calling for extra efficiencies, phasing out of operations or substitution of new roles to meet new areas of focus. A discernible shift has been towards understanding and matching institutional priorities through roles with an enhanced strategic focus and the increasing deployment of staffing in outreach roles (Schonfeld, 2016).

Affordability of journal content has been a growing challenge for academic libraries, exacerbated by slow progress towards open access until recently. Moves to shift subscription expenditure to the purchase of open access publishing services, modeled by the Max Planck Digital Library in 2015 (Schimmer et al., 2015), have resulted in libraries negotiating Publish and Read deals at institutional or consortium level. Such deals, while considered only a transitional measure towards full open access, at least consolidate two separate items of institutional expenditure to publishers for access and, via Article Processing Charges (APCs), for publication. Libraries are also likely to pay increasing attention to Open Educational Resources (OERs), the subject of growing interest for instructional purposes among US academics in the face of high textbook costs (Blankstein and Wolff-Eisenberg, 2019). Library identification of a free and open textbook at the University of California Los Angeles has resulted in welcome savings, estimated at \$57,000, for a class of 800 students (Steel, 2019). It can be expected that students will value such economies even more when struggling to pay tuition fees.

There are many ways, well documented in the literature, in which academic libraries contribute to institutional competitiveness. These include wider exposure of research outputs through open access publishing, library expertise in bibliometric analysis of publication impact, access to unique archival and special collections, and library buildings adapted or created as high technology, versatile learning and research environments. Such buildings offer opportunities to develop spaces in which students can develop a range of digital fluency proficiencies to enhance their employability prospects. Virginia Tech Libraries provide good examples of effective spaces, programs and partnerships with this focus (Mathews et al., 2018).

The increasingly consumerist student outlook, described earlier, is a factor for libraries to take into account. Perceiving students as clients or customers may be unappealing to some, but high expectations by fee-paying students of services, opening hours, access to information resources and responsiveness to issues raised should not be surprising. US library directors report difficulty in articulating the library's contributions to student success (Wolff-Eisenberg, 2017). This difficulty could be linked to a finding in a subsequent related survey that only half of US faculty see the library as highly important in contributing to student success (Blankstein and Wolff-Eisenberg, 2019, p. 62). Academic libraries may want to put some focus on raising that figure in future surveys. Table 2 summarizes economic factors and their influence on higher education and academic libraries.

Social factors influencing higher education

The PEST analysis methodology highlights demographics as a key social factor to consider and this holds true for higher education. Demographic trends influence the size of the student population and receive strong attention from higher education institutions for planning purposes. Patterns may vary for different countries. There is serious concern in the US about a "looming demographic storm" (Grawe, 2018, Introduction) which is expected to see a 15% drop in college-aged students in the five years from 2026. The UK, currently experiencing a decline in 18-year olds, expects to enjoy growth in this age group from 2021 (Universities UK, 2017, p. 3). Demographics affect the composition of the student population as well as its size, and the same UK study notes a growth in the size of the percentage of non-European Union students in the decade to 2015/15 when it stood at 13.5% (Universities UK, 2017, p. 49).

Increased numbers of international students represent only one element in the growth in diversity in the student population over recent decades. An Ithaka/OCLC study tracks changes since 1974, projecting forward to 2024 and presenting data across those five decades to show significantly higher percentages of students aged over 25, more females and part-timers, increased percentages of Black and Hispanic students and changes in socioeconomic class, with a greater representation of low and middle income populations (Malpas et al., 2018). The study identifies within the overall student population a group of new-traditional learners whose members "have at least one of the following attributes: they have no high school diploma, are enrolled more than one year after high school, are financially independent from parents, work full-time, or are responsible for children or other dependents" (Malpas et al., 2018, p. 15).

A much more diverse student body presents challenges for higher education institutions. Students may hold jobs or have family commitments, leaving limited time for study, and may expect more flexible, non-linear, pathways to academic qualifications. This calls on institutions to support modularized and disaggregated degrees, a long-term trend identified in the 2019 EDUCAUSE Higher Education Report (Alexander et al., 2019). Levels of academic preparedness can vary among new-traditional students, adding to the challenge of their commencement in higher education. More generally, concerns are expressed across the student population about new learning habits, including perceived declines in sustained reading (Blake & Gallimore, 2018) and in hours of study per week (Geiger, 2019). Half of the respondents to the 2018 Ithaka US Faculty Survey believed that their undergraduate students had poor skills related to locating and evaluating information (Blankstein and Wolff-Eisenberg, 2019, p. 45). These concerns translate into a prioritization of student success initiatives at higher education institutions to improve completion rates.

A related social concern is with student well-being and mental health. This has become a particularly significant issue for the student cohort aged 16–24 as it is recognized that this group faces a range of pressures. These include transition to college from non-traditional backgrounds, loan debt, stress from examinations and coursework and a competitive job market, in addition to changes in body, mind and social relationships (Johnson & Crenna-Jennings, 2018; Usher & Curran, 2017). More students are struggling to cope and there are reports of a

Table 2
Summary of economic factors and their influence

Economic factor	Impact on higher education	Implications for libraries
Lower state funding	Reliance on tuition fees	Reduced staffing, budgets
Cost control imperative	Efficiencies, centralization	Focus on lower content costs
Intensified competition	Reputation, ranking emphasis	Promoting competitive assets
Global market	International student focus	Support for internationalization
High tuition fees	Student debt, expectations	More demanding students
Employability	Curriculum adaptations	Enabling digital fluency

mental health crisis, with anxiety, depression and suicidality on the rise on US campuses (Chessman & Taylor, 2019). Other countries are experiencing similar issues and the number of young people in Britain seeking counseling over examination stress is reported to have increased by 200% in recent years (Brewerton & Woolley, 2016). A 2019 survey of US university presidents indicated that mental health was a greater concern than three years earlier for eight out of ten participants; the same percentage reported that student well-being featured in their university strategic plan, with 40% of plans highlighting student mental health specifically (Chessman & Taylor, 2019). Effective solutions have proved difficult to achieve and there is a realization that it may not be feasible to concentrate all support in counseling centers, placing some responsibility on staff in other units to assist.

Global issues with a strong social dimension are calling for the attention of higher education institutions. In 2015 all 193 United Nations member states adopted the UN Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015), a strategic framework of 17 interconnected goals whose target is a sustainable future for people and planet by 2030. The Goals aim to address issues such as climate change, biodiversity loss, poverty, hunger and gender inequality. Quality education is Goal 4 and underpins progress across all of the other goals. This creates a key role for higher education institutions and the publication *Getting started with the SDGs in universities* provides guidance (Sustainable Development Solutions Network Australia/Pacific, 2017). It emphasizes inclusive teaching and learning to prepare students for positive future influence on sustainability, interdisciplinary research to address global challenges, appropriate institutional governance and policies informed by the 17 Goals, and external leadership through public engagement. Institutions implementing these guidelines make sustainability a key focus of the curriculum and of the physical campus environment, engaging students with the critical thinking skills, problem-solving competencies and ethical approaches needed to address complex issues as global citizens.

Gender equality is Goal 5 of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and has become the focus of much attention in higher education. Deficits at individual institutions and in the sector as a whole have come to public notice in recent years; for example, data published by the European Commission reported that in 2017 women were heads of only 22% of Europe's higher education institutions and in 2016 held only 24% of Grade A Professor positions (European Commission, 2019). Institutions are expected to address gender equality issues and, more broadly, diversity and inclusion on campuses, recognizing that the inclusiveness in general of an institution may influence its attractiveness to international staff and students. Public funding may be linked to achieving performance targets related to equity (Brown et al., 2020).

Higher education engages public opinion. The 2019 Ithaka Next Wave conference ranked the public perception of higher education as the top challenge facing the sector (Ithaka, 2020). Pew Research Center surveys of US adults present a mixed picture (Parker, 2019). Public recognition in 2018 of the value of a degree for career success complemented strong appreciation by graduates in 2016. A separate 2018 survey found, however, that 61% of respondents perceived that the higher education system was going in the wrong direction. The top concerns expressed were high tuition fees and insufficient preparation of students for the workplace. Promotion of specific political standpoints on campus, or the protection of students from exposure to potentially offensive views, exercised half of the respondents.

Equality of opportunity is a strong societal focus, but there are concerns about equity of access to higher education. Reductions in public funding have promoted greater inequalities between institutions, in turn facilitating increasingly selective approaches to student recruitment by wealthier institutions (Geiger, 2019). Another issue compromising public confidence has been the exposure of unreliability in a significant number of research studies. This has been described as a "reproducibility crisis" (Sayre & Riegelman, 2018, p. 2) due to the

inability to verify findings in a high proportion of studies when using the published methodology. There is pressure on higher education to combat public distrust, generating calls for greater institutional focus on the public good (Connell, 2019; Fitzpatrick, 2019).

Implications for libraries

The increased diversity of the student body is a long-term trend, and support for new-traditional students has been an issue of concern for academic libraries for some time. Supporting student success emerged as the top priority for 80% of participants in the 2016 Ithaka survey of library directors (Wolff-Eisenberg, 2017, p. 57). Fister (2015) notes increased library engagement with partnering on a broader range of learning supports, including academic writing and English-language acquisition. A further progression in recent times has been towards library support for student well-being (Brewerton & Woolley, 2016; Ramsey & Aagard, 2018; Walton, 2018). Libraries claim some natural advantages in this area through their centrality on campus, trusted status, high degree of contact with students and willingness to adapt spaces and partner with others. Initiatives include well-being zones, self-help collections, creativity exercises and provision of food and drink at exam times. Cox and Brewster (Cox & Brewster, 2020) have challenged this trend, questioning whether some of these initiatives are superficial, sufficiently based on an understanding of the nature of student well-being issues or located within the professional knowledge base of libraries. These are legitimate questions but, given the challenges higher education institutions are experiencing with student mental health difficulties, library support is likely to be welcomed.

A study of perceptions of the future for academic libraries found a surprising lack of engagement among UK librarians with issues of global sustainability, based on interviews and a survey in 2017 (Cox, Pinfield, & Rutter, 2019a). This situation has been changing in line with the emphasis being placed by many institutions on supporting the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Libraries are contributing strongly through maximizing the sustainability of their buildings (Charney & Hauke, 2020), helping, for example, to promote good environmental practices among students. The 2019 EDUCAUSE Horizon Report for higher education identifies global digital equity as a significant challenge, highlighting not just equity of access to information but also equal opportunities to create content and collaborate in a distributed environment (Alexander et al., 2019). Academic libraries have a key role in helping to address these issues through digital literacy programs focused on skills development for content creation and sharing. Open access to publications, data and other research outputs, long promoted by libraries, is being recognized as vital in seeking to contain and treat global diseases. The negative impact of paywalls on addressing the Ebola pandemic has prompted a much more supportive publisher approach towards open access during the coronavirus crisis (Pells, 2020).

It is important for libraries to be sensitive to the heightened emphasis on equality, diversity and inclusion in higher education. This has a range of dimensions (Cruz, 2019), for example ensuring appropriate levels of diversity in the composition of staffing teams such that they adequately reflect the library's user base. The representativeness of library collections has also become a focus as the domination of subjects in the curriculum by long-established authors from a particular background is challenged, calling for collection development practices to be viewed through the lens of equality, diversity and inclusion (OCLC Research, 2017). Finally, academic libraries may be well positioned to help address another area of reputational anxiety for higher education institutions, namely concerns around the reproducibility of research studies. Libraries can leverage their skills in information retrieval, research data management and scholarly communications to contribute towards improved reproducibility (Sayre & Riegelman, 2018). Table 3 summarizes social factors and their influence on higher education and academic libraries.

Table 3
Summary of social factors and their influence

Social factor	Impact on higher education	Implications for libraries
Demographic trends	Shifts in student population	Changing user base
High educational participation	Diverse student profile, needs	New user support challenges
Student well-being	Increased mental health issues	Well-being initiatives
Global sustainability	Alignment with UN Goals	Equity, open access focus
Equality, diversity, inclusion	Equality targets and emphasis	Staffing, collections diversity
Public distrust of universities	Concerns about cost, skills, research	Support for reproducible research

Technological factors influencing higher education

Technology has, over time, fundamentally influenced higher education and continues to do so. The democratization of access to information has changed not only modes of teaching, learning and research but has also challenged academic structures and the pre-eminence of universities as sources, generators and interpreters of knowledge. This challenge to previously established authority extends to a paradigm shift in the role of the instructor from transmitting knowledge to facilitating student learning, giving rise to new, more flexible models. These include flipped classrooms whereby students study much of the introductory material about a subject in advance, enabling the lecture to provide more advanced and interactive coverage. Device ownership among students is typically high, creating expectations of technology-enabled education in order to meet the evolving needs of the labor market. These needs are in turn shaped by developments in technology which influence demand for academic programmes in new or existing subject areas. Keeping pace with technology can be a challenge for higher education institutions. For example, a UK survey in 2019 identified limited preparedness for the age of artificial intelligence (Pells, 2019).

Online learning is well established, offering opportunities to open up access to different audiences and to generate institutional revenue. From a student perspective convenience and cost, supported by effective technology platforms, make online education attractive. The provider experience is not always straightforward, however. Academic staff may struggle to replicate their traditional teaching online, may find the technology difficult or time-consuming, and may have concerns about their autonomy and ownership of course materials (Marcum, 2014). There is recognition of the challenges of developing digital fluency among academic staff and maximizing strong collaboration with specialist online instructional designers (Alexander et al., 2019). Since early 2020 the coronavirus pandemic has been forcing the hand of higher education institutions towards online learning as the default platform for students unable to attend campuses. This potentially creates longer-term momentum towards ubiquitous online delivery (Lau et al., 2020).

There is no shortage of technologies available or in development to enhance the learning experience. The 2020 *EDUCAUSE Horizon Report, Teaching and Learning Edition* highlights adaptive (personalized) learning, artificial intelligence, extended reality and the use of analytics to improve student success, providing examples of these technologies in use at many institutions worldwide (Brown et al., 2020). Recent years have seen growth in the use of learning analytics to select students and particularly to identify those at risk of non-completion and in need of feedback or support. These practices also generate privacy concerns about how data are used.

Research too has undergone transformation through technology. Shared network access globally promotes collaborative, team-based and cross-institutional research and a doubling of the number of internationally co-authored scientific papers occurred between 1990 and 2011 (Dempsey & Malpas, 2018, p. 73). Evolving technology infrastructures, platforms and workflow tools have facilitated this trend, also delivering increased access to a range of research materials besides the final, formal, publication, usually a journal article or monograph. Such

interim materials may include laboratory notebooks, questionnaires, software codes and datasets. There has been an increased expectation, especially from research funders, that final publications and interim outputs should be available on an open access basis. In the case of research data this raises a range of issues. These include restrictions due to confidentiality or intellectual property considerations, the costs involved in managing data effectively and the development of more flexible academic reward systems to recognize effort around open data and outputs other than articles in established journals (J. Ross, 2020). Research has become increasingly data-driven across all disciplines, not just the sciences, and digital scholarship encompasses the advance of digital humanities research.

Artificial intelligence is expected to exert a strong influence on the future of higher education (Gleason, 2018; Pells, 2019; Penprase, 2018). It may be defined as the development of computing capacity to process vast amounts of data, enabling the development of machine learning and cognitive intelligence in support of automated prediction and decision-making. Excitement around potential applications has been accompanied by serious ethical concerns regarding issues of privacy, algorithmic bias, surveillance and responsible use of data. The implications for society, and indeed for higher education, are profound. There are forecasts that 40% to 50% of jobs will disappear in the next 15–30 years (Pells, 2019) and that 65% of school-age children in 2018 will graduate into an employment market consisting of jobs not yet in existence (Alexander et al., 2019, p. 27). For higher education institutions this may translate into a dynamically evolving, multidisciplinary, curriculum encompassing technology and ethics. The goal will be to meet demand for new skills by employers and for lifelong learning by students striving to keep pace with changing technologies and applications. Artificial intelligence may reduce administrative effort, contribute to student assessment, make learning more personalized, and support research by participating in the generation and testing of scientific hypotheses (Pells, 2019).

Implications for libraries

Just as higher education institutions have needed to adapt to new technology-driven paradigms, academic libraries have had to re-position their offering. Users have many options regarding access to information and the 2018 Ithaka survey of US faculty showed that participants considered materials freely available online to be almost as important as library collections or subscriptions (Blankstein and Wolff-Eisenberg, 2019, p. 19). The same survey found that 22% of respondents saw the role played by librarians as becoming much less important due to easy access to academic content online (Blankstein and Wolff-Eisenberg, 2019, pp. 56–57). Libraries have experienced disintermediation through increased academic use of networked discovery, workflow and sharing tools such as Google Scholar, Mendeley and ResearchGate. Their response has been to diversify library roles throughout the learning and research cycles, adopting an engagement-based strategy (Dempsey & Malpas, 2018, pp. 76–79).

Libraries have increasingly hosted a range of learning technologies in recent times, leveraging their position as accessible, often centrally located, spaces on campus. There has been significant growth in the development of makerspaces in libraries, making available diverse

technologies to enable students to create physical objects and to develop creative and entrepreneurial skills (Nichols et al., 2017). These developments are part of an established trend to reconceptualize and redesign library buildings as technology-enabled spaces to support active learning and collaboration beyond the lecture venue. As one article summarizes it, “Libraries are repositioning themselves as laboratories for exploration, incubators for ideas, and essential collaborators across the teaching, learning, and research enterprises.” (Mathews et al., 2018, p. 52).

Beyond physical spaces, libraries are taking strong roles in promoting digital literacy among students, with an emphasis on the skills and responsibilities involved in creating and sharing digital content. Related to this is the responsible use of personal data. Librarians have been prominent in promoting digital citizenship among students but also in advising institutions on the appropriate balance between privacy and business needs in using learning analytics for student success (Wetzel et al., 2020). One further consideration for libraries is their effectiveness in reaching online learners. An OCLC study in 2014 reported that only 39% of learners who had taken an online class towards a degree had used the library (De Rosa et al., 2014, p. 73). It is possible that this figure could be specific to the relatively small sample surveyed or might reflect some ambiguity between use of the physical or online library. Nevertheless, libraries may want to reflect on how to ensure maximum uptake in a scenario, already noted, where online delivery will increase significantly as a longer-term consequence of the 2020 coronavirus outbreak.

The role of academic libraries in research has expanded in recent years to include open access, open scholarship, impact measurement, digital scholarship and research data management. These new areas of engagement have called for different staffing arrangements, often generating new roles and multi-professional team configurations (Mulligan, 2016). As research has become more collaborative and interdisciplinary, libraries have faced a dilemma in terms of organizing staffing support for research according to subject or function (Hoodless & Pinfield, 2018). The increased availability of a wider range of interim materials in addition to final research outputs, coupled with much stronger recent momentum in favor of open access, places more emphasis on the role of the library as a curator and publisher. The current impetus towards open access, including via transitional Publish and Read agreements, raises the question of how libraries might adapt to a future in which this access model becomes universal. Attention to this scenario has been limited to date but is likely to grow.

Finally, artificial intelligence confronts libraries with many possibilities and challenges. These range from machine-readable collections, roles in data supply and curation and in data literacy training to concerns about the required skills base for librarians, job losses and disintermediation by more agile external solutions providers (Cox, Pinfield, & Rutter, 2019c). While there is recognition of the significance of artificial intelligence for the future of the library profession, there is also a sense of limited awareness, combined with a high degree of uncertainty regarding potential impact (Pinfield et al., 2017; Wheatley & Hervieux, 2019). Table 4 summarizes technological factors and their influence on higher education and academic libraries.

Conclusion

This article set out to examine the key political, economic, social and technological factors influencing higher education and their implications for libraries. Its findings show that trends across each of these four dimensions have wrought major changes in higher education over the past two decades. Politically, state policy often means a combination of competition for funding, rigorous accountability, increased pressure and considerable disgruntlement on campuses. The economic climate is challenging and its key features in many countries include high tuition fees, loan debt, intense competition to attract students and to meet their expectations of value for money and employability. Social trends have resulted in a larger and more diverse student body which may experience a range of challenges at university, including issues of well-being. Higher education institutions are increasingly conscious of their obligations to society, paying greater attention to global sustainability, gender equality and public perceptions. Technology has delivered both opportunities and threats, democratizing access to information, facilitating online learning and collaborative, data-driven, research, and promising new possibilities alongside ethical concerns through artificial intelligence.

The higher education environment represents a key operating context for academic libraries. Changes in higher education have implications for academic libraries, presenting a range of challenges and opportunities. Challenges include competing for resources, proving value, doing more with less, meeting the needs and expectations of an evolving student body and leveraging new technologies. There is a need to deal with uncertainty on an ongoing basis, while striving to keep the library prominent in the thinking of institutional leaders. Academic libraries have embraced significant opportunities too. Among these are new roles in learning and research, concerted global action towards open access to journals especially, the growing influence of open scholarship and the value of library buildings as facilitators of collaborative, technology-enabled learning. Overarching all of these is a recognition of the importance of traditional library values such as generosity, openness and public good at a time when higher education institutions are engaging more strongly with their societal responsibilities.

Change for higher education and libraries has been characterized in recent years by its pace and ongoing nature. Opportunities to pause have been rare and this looks set to continue in the wake of the 2020 global coronavirus pandemic which has had devastating human, social and economic impact internationally. Its long-term consequences for higher education will emerge fully over time. A deep global economic recession of uncertain duration is anticipated. One commentator has considered the possible effects of a 5% to 15% contraction in global GDP, envisaging severe impact on the affordability of higher education with the likelihood that it may take at least five years for a return to 2019 student numbers (Marginson, 2020). Other concerns include negative impact on international student recruitment, the future of institutions already struggling financially before the crisis, further reductions in state funding and how to enhance online learning as a mainstreamed rather than supplementary delivery platform.

The coronavirus crisis is set to affect the future of higher education profoundly. Nevertheless, it seems likely that the influence of the

Table 4
Summary of technological factors and their influence

Technological factor	Impact on higher education	Implications for libraries
Ease of access to information	Authority challenged	Disintermediation
Mass ownership of devices	E-learning, new paradigms	Engaging remote learners
Learning technologies	Enhanced learning experience	Opportunities to host
Research platforms	Collaborative, sharing focus	Open access expectations
Data-driven research	New opportunities, practices	Data management roles
Artificial intelligence advances	Teaching, research changes	Roles, skills, ethical concerns

factors described in this article will endure while also changing in nature and extent according to circumstances in different geographic areas. Monitoring the higher education environment will remain vital for libraries, as will understanding the political, economic, social and technological factors shaping their immediate operations and future strategies.

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None.

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